

Mapping Immersive Geovisualization Design: A Typology of VR Approaches in Geoscience Educational Applications

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Abstract. Significant growth in immersive virtual reality (IVR) for geoscience research and education has been driven by advances in head-mounted displays (HMDs), accessibility of game engines and enhanced geospatial data acquisition methods over the past decade. Applications span the fields of geology, volcanology, geoheritage, or cartography, and range from virtual field trips (VFTs) to interactive climate visualisations. This poster presents a typology of design approaches in Immersive Virtual Reality (IVR) for geoscience educational applications. The typology was derived from a systematic analysis of 37 papers describing the design, development and implementation of IVR systems between 2013 and 2024. We coded each paper across five dimensions: (1) geospatial data input types, (2) IVR platforms/display devices, (3) application domains, (4) spatial interaction modes, and (5) evaluation approaches. Categories emerged iteratively from the data rather than being imposed a priori. Key findings revealed significant diversity in geospatial data, with three dominant pathways: unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based photogrammetry, 360° panoramic imagery, and LiDAR-derived point clouds. Although HMD-based systems are dominant, WebVR platforms have emerged since 2020 as more accessible alternatives. The largest application cluster is VFTs for geology and geomorphology education. Despite the potential for rich 3D interaction, most systems implement simple models, such as passive navigation or basic measurement tools. More sophisticated interactions, such as problem-solving queries or multi-user collaboration, remain rare. Design documentation consistently exceeds empirical evaluation. This typology provides researchers and developers with a reference framework that maps the current design landscape and identifying underexplored opportunities, such as multi-user collaborative environments or real-time data integration.

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1 Introduction

Over the past decade, advances in HMDs, game engine accessibility, and sophisticated geospatial data acquisition methods have driven significant traction for IVR technologies in geoscience research and education. IVR applications span geology, volcanology, geoheritage, cartography, and wayfinding, and range from virtual field trips to interactive climate visualisations. This poster demonstrates how these systems are designed, what geospatial data sources are used, which platforms are chosen, what interaction paradigms are implemented, and for what purposes.

Furthermore, the poster addresses this gap by presenting a typology of design approaches in IVR for geoscience applications, derived from a systematic analysis of 37 papers describing the design, development, and implementation of IVR systems.

2 Methods

These papers were identified during a broader systematic review but were excluded from the main analysis as they focused on technical design and workflows rather than empirical evaluation. We systematically coded each paper across five dimensions to map the current design landscape: (1) types of geospatial data input, (2) IVR platforms/display devices, (3) application domains, (4) spatial interaction modes and (5) evaluation approaches.

We conducted a structured content analysis of 37 papers published between 2013 and 2024, coding each one according to the five dimensions listed above. The papers were sourced from journals in the fields of geoscience, cartography and educational technology, with a focus on systems that were explicitly designed for geoscience education. Coding was performed iteratively, with categories emerging from the data rather than being imposed a priori. For instance, geospatial data sources were classified into categories such as UAV/photogrammetry, LiDAR point clouds, 360° panoramas, procedurally modelled terrain, or multi-source fusion workflows. Platform types included HMDs, cave automatic virtual environment (CAVE) systems, or hybrid configurations. Application domains ranged from VFTs in geology and geomorphology to geoheritage communication, structural geology field mapping, and scientific visualization of atmospheric or climate data.

3 Results

Among the key findings were the following:

Geospatial data diversity. The analysis shows that there is a variety of geospatial data sources, with three main ways of getting this data: (a) UAV-based photogrammetry workflows that produce textured 3D meshes; (b) 360° panoramic imagery used in the development of VFTs; and (c) LiDAR-derived point clouds used in structural geology applications. Some applications use a greater variety of geospatial layers, integrating photogrammetry, thematic layers, digital elevation models (DEMs) or field annotations.

Platform fragmentation. HMD-based systems remain dominant, however, for instance WebVR platforms have emerged as a pragmatic alternative, particularly since 2020. This has been driven by the need for accessibility during the pandemic and the desire to reach a broader audience without requiring specialized hardware. CAVE systems persist in niche applications, while hybrid systems acknowledge the reality of heterogeneous user environments.

Virtual field trips dominate application domains. VFTs for geology and geomorphology education represent the largest use case cluster, followed by general geography education and geoheritage/geotourism. Structural geology field mapping tools form a distinct secondary cluster, emphasizing measurement, annotation and data export capabilities over purely visual exploration.

Spatial interaction remains limited. Despite the potential for rich 3D interaction, most systems implement relatively simple interaction paradigms. Passive

navigation and viewing, or basic measurement and annotation tools, dominate. More sophisticated interactions, such as true geographic information system (GIS)-integrated queries, multi-user collaboration or agent-based simulations, are discussed in theory but rarely implemented.

Design documentation exceeds empirical evaluation.

Consistent with our sampling strategy, most papers focus on system design, workflow documentation or platform demonstration. Where evaluation occurs, it is often technical (performance benchmarks, accuracy assessments) rather than user focused. Heuristic expert reviews and small-scale pilot user tests often substitute for controlled experimental design.

3 Conclusion and implications

This typology provides a framework for researchers, educators and developers working with geospatial technologies and immersive visualisation. It maps the current design landscape and highlights under-explored opportunities, such as multi-user collaborative GIS environments and real-time data integration. It also clarifies ongoing developments and suggests evaluation priorities, such as comparing the learning outcomes of 360° systems and HMDs and assessing the added value of interactive versus passive systems. For the broader geospatial community, it shows that IVR in the geosciences has evolved from proof-of-concept demonstrations into a diverse and technically sophisticated, but still fragmented landscape.

Data and Software Availability Section

This paper analyses publicly available academic literature. All analysed papers are accessible through their respective publishers and fully cited with DOIs in the References section. The coding framework is described in the Methods section.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for writing process to improve the readability and language of the manuscript, mainly grammar improving, but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

Author Contributions

Author1: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. Author2: Conceptualization, Data curation, Resources, Supervision, Validation.

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